

Traditional Institutions and Conflict Resolution in Nigeria: A Social Work Analysis

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Abstract

Traditional institutions in African societies and elsewhere are known to hold sacred peacemaking processes from historical antecedence before the disruption by colonial administration that introduced adjudication and arbitration, but which is often deemed the converse of traditional methods of conflict resolution. Contemporary patterns of conflict resolution are rather flawed in dealing with the challenges posed by modern conflict in Nigeria. This paper therefore examines the role of traditional institutions in conflict resolution in Nigeria from a social work perspective. Data was generated from secondary sources only. The study was anchored in system theory of Ludwig Bertalanffy (1956). The study revealed that the traditional conflict resolution method as practiced in Nigeria is better than the modern adjudicative method of conflict resolution, because it is faster and non-adversarial. The study recommends among other things a reversal to traditional methods of conflict management and resolution, because it is friendlier, faster, cheaper and devoid of post conflict resolution animosity.

Key words: Conflict, traditional institutions, culture, social work and resolution.

Introduction

Prior to colonial incursion into Africa, many African societies had a well laid down traditional process of conflict resolution. Various communities in Africa had different conventions aimed at mitigating inter-human, intra- and inter-communal crises. According to Woko and Osagie (2014), these conventions were backed by taboo which must be adhered to for peaceful regulation of human activities, and relationship among community members.

In Africa, many cultural groups has adopted good dispute resolution mechanisms that has helped in resolving conflict that was very peculiar to their own ways before the advent of British rule. These traditional mechanisms are built on traditions and customs and were culturally effectual for resolving conflict within their communities. Such methods of conflict resolution among cultural entities in Nigeria were based on the information that was conceded down from one generation to another (Ajayi, 2014). However, with the introduction of western civilization, some of the traditional methods of conflict resolution are being gradually wrinkled. Most Nigerians, specifically urban dwellers, have a preference to use the modern or conventional method of conflict resolution which is based on the criminal justice administrative system (Ajayi, 2014)

In spite of the western influence, traditional mechanisms are still being used in most African countries in order to keep communities in harmony. Zartman (2009) observed that in traditional African societies, the understanding of conflict was based on the disaffection between the humans and the supernatural (example; deities, ancestors and supreme beings). The African methods of conflict resolution relies on mediation, negotiation, dialogue with thw use of traditional rulers, security committees and religious leaders. It is also less expensive and based on the principle of maintaining relationship. The intent of this emphasis on relationship is to restore

harmony among the disputants and also provide a means of restitution through apology and compensation, especially where damages have been caused to any of the parties. More importantly, the traditional conflict resolution methods were aimed at resolving disputes and not necessarily pronouncing judgments. However, this is based on the philosophy of reconciliation and peaceful settlement between the parties rather than acrimony.

Problem statement

The persistence of violent conflict in Nigeria's rural and sub-urban communities may have been attributed to weak traditional methods in conflict management (Woko & Osagie, 2014). Despite the increased attention and improved knowledge about conflict management in the post-colonial war era, incidents of conflict in Nigeria seem to have eluded international as well as domestic efforts to bring them under control (Crocker, Hampson, and Aall, 1996; Zartman and Rasmussen, 1997). This explains the reasons why the traditional African method provides a better alternative than the modern method for resolution of complex conflicts engulfing many countries in Africa. The traditional African method here refers to the use of traditional institutions such as Council Elders, Chief and Age Grade groups for conflict resolution. It could also refer to the use of alternative dispute resolution mechanisms which involve mediation, formation of security committees, reconciliation, dialogue, negotiations and religious institutions to resolve conflict. On the other hand, the modern method of conflict resolution entails the use of the criminal justice system like the court, police, correctional service (prisons) and community established security outfits or surveillance teams. For instance, Ajayi and Buhari (2014) contended that traditional methods and strategies employed in dispute resolution before colonial involvement in Africa offered greater prospects for peaceful co-existence and harmonious relationships in post-conflict

periods than the modern method of litigation in law courts. They also stated that traditional African societies had a well-structured, time proven social system that was geared towards reconciliation, maintenance and improvement of social relationships.

Stemming from the above, this paper examines the role of traditional institutions in conflict resolution in Nigeria. Although the indigenous method has been affected by colonialism and modernization, particularly with the introduction of the formal legal systems of court of justices, different ethnic groups in Nigeria are still attuned to their traditional method of dealing with conflict.

Theoretical Framework

System Theory

System theory was first propounded by Ludwig Von Bertalanffy in 1956. Other exponents of the theory include the sociologists Talcott Parsons and Robert Merton, among others. Bertalanffy sees the system as a multifaceted interacting element uncluttered and intermingling with its environments, in mutually part-to-whole and whole-to-part relationships enabling networks between the different components that fit together in a whole (Ngwu, 2014).

A very insightful definition of a system which may be seen as the basis of the utilization of the concept in many discipline such as Sociology, Social Work Political science among others has been offered by Kast and Rosendwing (1972). According to them, the concept “system” refers to “an organized, unitary whole composed of two or more interdependent parts, components, or subsystems and delineated by identifiable boundaries from its environmental supra system” (Kast, et al., 1972, p, 2). In this sense, system implies a whole, made up of interdependent and co-operating parts which even though identifiable on its own right exists within the context of a larger

environment. The components or parts of a system may exist in the form of institutions, techniques, devices, procedures, plans, races, professions and people. But for a system to facilitate the achievement of a given goal, the interdependence and interrelation between the parts is very important.

As Anugwom (2010) observes, it is this interdependence among components that essentially defines a system. In this case, a system is usually goal or consequence oriented and the parts interact in order to facilitate this. Each component of a system may also be seen as a sub system of the system. But beyond this fact is the more crucial realization that it is the relationships and interactions between these sub-systems or components that explain and determine the behavior of the whole (system) (Anugwom, 2010).

The system theory is very significant in explaining a study of this nature. This is because the age grade, council of elders, and religious institution, among other traditional institutions as integral institutions of the communities, have made significant contributions in maintaining peace and order in Nigeria. The various traditional institutions are subsystems contributing their quota toward the stability of the country.

Conceptual and methodological framework

Conflict refers to any disagreement between two or more parties, while conflict management refers to the method that is used to resolve and manage conflict between parties in order to avoid a reoccurrence and provide justice. It is also the process of reducing the negative aspect of conflict, while increasing the positive aspect of conflict. Significantly, conflict management is the ability to be able to identify and handle conflict in a way that proffers a lasting solution to the problem while keeping the relationship between the parties in conflict. The concept

of conflict management is also synonymous with dispute resolution (Daudu, 2009). Traditional conflict management refers to those methods of conflict management that have been practiced for an extended period of time and have evolved within a people in a particular society, and used as a means of settling dispute. However, legal form of conflict resolution refers to the legal procedure to conflict resolution using government approved institutions such as the law court, police, correctional service (prisons) and other security personnel established by the state.

Methodologically, this study was imbedded in a literature survey approach and as such was both historical and exploratory in nature. The study had no time bound while the data for the study was completely secondary. Secondary data was sourced for existing desktop literature relevant to the study

Literature Review

Overview of Traditional Institutions, conflict resolution and social work practice

Traditional institutions refer to the indigenous socio-political arrangements whereby leaders with proven track records are appointed and installed in line with the provisions of their native laws and customs (Orji & Olali, 2010). The fundamental essence of the institutions is to preserve the customs and traditions of the people, to manage conflicts arising among or between members of the community by the instrumentality of laws and customs of the people and bind the society in a harmonious manner. They are the active agents of maintaining the social equilibrium or order and building peace in the respective societies (Nweke, 2012).

The traditional dispute resolution method is also very effective in deterring future offenders, because the offence is usually seen as against the community rather than the individual.

Nwanko and Nzeribe (1990) in Akinwale (2010) noted that Africans believe in the concept of

communalism because of their belief that the individual is not alone, but under an umbrella of the community. Therefore, the conflict resolution was based on internalized values which include honesty, openness, empathy, community solidarity and individual loyalty to the group. It was usually believed that individuals who come before the community for dispute settlement should be sincere otherwise they are seen as having committed an offence against the community rather than the individual concerned.

Traditional institutions enjoy unconditional validity and acceptability within a specific social or community setting in Nigeria. Traditional institutions are rooted in/by products of the broad social philosophy and cultural worldview of a specific community. The ontological paradigm of such communities consists of certain values and customs which they consider to be representative of their identity and useful to their social, political and ecological surroundings.

Traditional African legal anthropological research (customarily approved methods of dispute resolution through diffusion) focused on differentiating between customs and law (Gibbs, 1963). For the most part, the absence of written codes or statutes in indigenous (pre-colonial) Africa was a major defining characteristic of custom – an immemorial traditional social order, largely immutable and closely linked to the cultural system (Uwazie, 1994). The view of simpler or indigenous societies dominated by integrated traditions of maintaining peace and order distinguished them from modern states with laws (Bohannan, 1957). Hence statutes or judicially declared rules or social control – deliberately, respectively, and rationally made by trained professionals - became the essence of justice in both colonial and independent African nation-states. However, persistent and serious problems in the current formal or official (modern) legal

system throughout Africa have created a type of “law nostalgia”, a search for rediscovery of and adaptation to traditional or indigenous African management systems (Nwazie, 1991; Ayittey, 1991; Albert et al. 1995).

Relevant literature on dispute processing and conflict resolution proposes conflict handling forums and procedures of dispute resolution typologies such as mediation, negotiation, arbitration, litigation, self-defense, avoidance, and “lumping it” variables such as the nature of relationships, socio-economic statuses, the nature of the dispute and the disputants experience allow for explanations of the choice of the various conflict management strategies (Merry, 1979; Abel, 1973).

In Africa, historically, there were various levels of conflict resolution: There were dispute resolution at the interpersonal or family level, the extended family level and village or town level where the Chief in Council presided. These tiers represented the political unit that makes up the community (Ajayi, 2014). Conflicts were effectively resolved at these various tiers because disputants considered themselves as part of a larger community through which their dispute are resolved. However, social workers intervention in conflict resolution has been a new theory and practices since their operation requires a peaceful environment for practice. The social worker in conflict resolution plays a silent role but supportive to policy formulation for advocacy and intervention.

However, as a helping profession, The Nigerian Association of Social Workers (NASOW) sees the profession as an activity of assisting individuals, group or communities to enhance or restore their capacity for social functioning and to create societal conditions favourable to their goals (Zastrow 1999 in Ngwu, 2014). As part of the profession’s mandate, the purpose of social

work is to enhance, promote social harmony and link people so that they can cope with their social environment. Social work enhances the coping capacity of people or discovers the problem solving capacity of people (Ngwu, 2014). As a helping profession, Social workers are also charged with the fundamental role of linking people with systems that provide them with resources, opportunities and services within their social milieu. Social workers are to ensure that people are adequately cared and provided for by the system

Traditional institutions and their mechanisms in conflict resolution in Nigeria

The traditional institutions in the Nigerian context are inclusive of the chiefs-in-council, elders-in-council, title holders, and Military retirees who may be appointed based on their contributions to the growth and development of their communities with little or no executive, legislative or judicial powers. Among the Niger Delta communities specifically, the traditional approaches to conflict management and resolution vary from community to community, especially when viewed from the multi-cultural or multi-ethnic composition of the region. However, most of the Niger Delta communities share common traditional approaches, especially the *Igbo* and *Ijaw* speaking groups in view of their common historical antecedents - oil exploration and exploitation (Nweke,2012).

Two major types of traditional institutions existed in pre-colonial Nigeria. These include centralised authority structures and de-centralised authority structures. The Hausa/Fulani pre-colonial society falls within the centralised structure whereas, the Igbo society/South-East, was a de-centralised system. However, the Yoruba pre-colonial society had a combination of both. In Nigerian traditional societies, there were a plethora of structures and values in place, for example, centralised political systems with strong monarchies existed. Furthermore, just like other Nigerian

traditional societies, governance was carried out within the framework of communities, such as the *Arochukwu* community, compounds which were a decentralized structure in local governance within local communities, such as the *Agbo-ile* among the Yoruba; and ‘house’ which were a unique institution in local governance in the Niger Delta communities such as the Canoe Houses of Bonny and Kalabari in Rivers State (Roberts, 2004). These kingdoms were, however, presided over by strong traditional institutions corresponding to the geopolitics of tradition. Before colonialism, traditional rulers were the sovereign authorities within their respective jurisdiction. They were selected by common consensus and conflicting issues were resolved through customary practices (Nweke: 2012).

In the Niger Delta, most of the kingdoms were highly decentralised to lower units of governance from traditional rulers to smaller or compound/village chiefs, elders-in-council, age grades and the like (Roberts, 2004). In a traditional setting in the Niger Delta communities, a council of kingmakers was responsible for selecting the successor to a deceased ruler or most elderly or village head. *Amanyinabos*, (Ijaw kingdom), *Okan-Obolo* (Andoni), *Obara-Yok* (Yok-Obolo), the national deity), *Nye-Nwe-Alis* and *Owho*-holders (Ikwerre Ethnic Nationality) *Eze-Ogbah* (Ogbah of Northern Niger Delta) were some of the influential traditional institutions in the Niger Delta which all had very strong influences in their respective localities in conflict management and controlling peace. These traditional institutions serve as the custodian of their people’s customs and traditions. This extends to other ethnic nationalities of Ekpeye, Ndoni, Etche, Ogoni, among others. Traditional institutions had their own innovative measures to resolve conflict over issues like marital conflict, land clash, hostility over natural resource management, inter-community conflict etc.

Traditional methods of social control such as communal solidarity, traditional oaths, rewards, vigilantes, informal settlements, checks and balances, decentralization, effective communication and good governance remain strong and have been informally used successfully for conflict management by these communities in Nigeria. Such institutions opted for oaths for the offender and even declared prize (generally in the form of material objects) for one who admitted it. In matters of larger issues of inter community and intra community clashes (for instance in case of war like situations), opinions of the elders and the experts were asked for from experts in warfare and were taken seriously (Akinwale, 2010). If the traditional head or the rulers were found guilty or corrupted, there were even evidences of self-exile, suicide or resignation from the post as it was against the group he/she belonged to. The group/collective identity mattered the most and anything disturbing the peace and harmony was considered crime. In such instances punishments varied from fiscal fine to physical punishments. Transparency in the use of power and the provision for the public to question the leaders marked the uniqueness of such mechanisms .To maintain social solidarity and collective identity were the basic objectives in matters of resolution (ibid, 2010). It thus helped building a sustainable peaceful co-existence.

Discussion and Conclusion

The involvement of a third party is significant in this practice of conflict resolution because it reveals the basic nature of mediation in African traditional conflict resolution. In these practice of conflict resolution the role of the mediator is to help parties reach a solution to their problem and to arrive at an outcome that both parties are happy to accept. Mediators avoid taking sides, making judgments or giving guidance. They are simply responsible for developing effective communications and building consensus between the parties. The focus of a mediation meeting is

to reach a common sense settlement agreeable to both parties in a case. Though there is not any legal compulsion to follow or disobey the suggestions; people under sheer faith, group identity and cultural loyalty follow these recommendations. As society is a system with many parts, all the parts are expected to work interdependently to for the good of the entire system. The system theory is applied to the social system such as groups, families and societies (Payne, 2005). However, these groups have been identified as systems because they interact with each other in some definable ways. It was therefore believed that due to the wholeness of the system, a conflict in any part of the system affects the system as a whole and its parts. For instance, Nigeria as a nation is system that needs peace so that the entire system can function optimally for the good of the entire society. If any part is riddled with conflict, the entire system cannot function effectively because a part of it has been affected

The importance of agreement, compromise, forgiveness are the basic features of the negotiation practices of the traditional mechanisms of conflict resolution and peace. From the discourse above, the study proves that peace is a necessity for societal growth and development. Though not structured in the proper term, mechanisms discussed above do follow a certain process to reach a desirable peaceful end which includes: preparation, discussion, clarification of goals, and negotiation towards a Win-Win outcome, agreement, implementation of a course of action. In this aspect, these mechanisms are found to share the same nature of modern negotiation methods. During situations when there is failure to agree, then re-scheduling a further meeting is called for. Attempts have been made for more viable solution with more discussion and sometimes, it becomes more informal process of negotiation and resolution.

The above description proves that methods practiced by the traditional institutions are people centric, liberal, flexible and restorative in nature. Traditional Institutional mechanisms throughout Africa not only Nigeria is in continuous processes to offer justice and bring harmony by simple, accessible and local mechanisms which at the same time are cost effective and time saving. This economic aspect matters a lot in the popularity of these methods even in the recent times.

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